

COMPARING INVESTMENT PATTERNS OF GOVERNMENT AND PRIVATE SECTOR EMPLOYEES IN GANDHINAGAR AND KALOL: A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The behaviour of investors towards mutual fund investment keeps changing over the time due to many reasons. Their behaviour is affected through many different factors like return on investment, perceived risk, liquidity of funds, safety of invested funds, etc. Their choice of mutual fund option which better fits to invest their money is based on the information available to them, their ability to analyse that information, and expected future growth and safety of that option. In this study the researcher selected investors from private sector as well as public sector as a work segment from urban and semi urban area of Gujarat and collected their responses to study their investment intention, return on investment expectations, the influencing factors, perceived risk in investing, the investment selection decision and their investment pattern behind investing in mutual funds. The researcher collected the data through structured questionnaire and analysed it with the help of different statistical tools and reached the conclusion that majority of the investors save only 20% of their income and they start investing in the early age of their life (20-30 years). Investors from urban area focuses mainly children education and their marriage purpose behind their investments while investors from semi urban area give more importance to their retirement age to manage unforeseen emergency situations and chooses the options which give more and consistent return to them after discussing with their family members.

KEYWORDS: Mutual Fund, Investment, Investor behaviour

INTRODUCTION

Investment is the use of excess funds or savings with the aim of obtaining some positive return in the future (HAYES, 2023). The investment spectrum today is huge and includes financial and non-financial products (ASMUNDSON, 2016). Financial products include bank deposits, stock markets, commodity markets, insurance, postal programs, mutual funds and bonds etc. Non-financial products include real estate and gold/jewellery.

Investors' ideas about various investment alternatives vary greatly from customer to customer and it is determined by multiple demographic, economic and cognitive factors. Postal schemes and fixed deposits are not much popular among people (OJHA, 2023). Investors invest hard-earned money to get financial security for such investments in the future. But before making an investment decision and choosing a financial path, they go through a process of cognitive decision-making that guides them in choosing the path (Seraj, Elham Alzain, & Ali Saleh Alshebam, 2022). Investors sometimes lack knowledge of the various options available and therefore struggle to make a good investment decision (WAGNER, 2022).

Many people in India prefer government jobs (TANDON, 2023). The main reason is job security as well as other facilities like accommodation, transportation, health and other benefits. In private sectors, these facilities are restricted to employees up to certain level. Even though the salary is lower compared to the private sector, the presence of benefits increases the value of government job (MAKRIDIS, 2021). Government employees are more likely to receive retirement benefits from their employer and enjoy more stability in their jobs compared to private sector employees (SINGH, 2023). Additionally, private sector employees are more vulnerable to market forces, including wage levels that adjust to fluctuating market conditions (Johnson, 2020). Due to all these factors, public sector employees' investment pattern differs to save a larger portion of their income compared to private sector employees. The present research is focusing on the study and analysis in the difference in the investment preference between the two industry personnel and determine the reasons behind the same.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Plenty of research carried out to study the awareness of mutual funds, the preference of various investment options and the investment pattern of investors. People in India are well aware about mutual funds and consider mutual funds as a risk-free investment instrument (PATEL, 2020) Majority of investors tend to prefer the lowest risk investments such as bank deposits and insurance plans and have a mixed investment horizon (RAO & DR. ANKITA PATEL, 2020). When we talk about investment awareness among working women the level of popularity of working women is not significantly related to age, occupation and educational qualifications. The investment preferences of the respondents indicated a safe investment attitude. Bank deposits and gold were popular investment options for most people (Atchyuthan & Rathirani Yogendrarajah, 2017)

Investment priorities such as return, risk, security, liquidity and investment maturity and to study investors' preferences regarding various investment options leads to conduct a study to compare the investment behaviour of government and private employees, and it concludes to some extent that instruments or products such as stocks or state securities have performed well in the past, and the instruments and products supported with strong requirements will continue to perform well in the future too (Jayaprakash, Linzy Ajayan, & Jayashankar. J, 2017). There exist various factors affecting investment decisions of government and private employees and leading to examine the investment preference and risk perception of public and private sector employees. In previous research on comparison of investment pattern between public and private sector employees (THANGAMEENA & DR. K. NITHYA, 2019), it was concluded that private sector investors are likely to invest more than they save from their income, while public sector investors are likely to save more than they invest from their income (where saving is a short or mid-term financial goal and investment is a long-term financial goal).

To analyse the saving habits and investment patterns of the employees and analyse the investment selection behaviour of the employees in Chandigarh Sood & Dr. Navdeep Kaur (2015) have concluded that the most preferred investment options are LIC and bank deposits and most of the factors influencing the investment decision are high returns, tax benefits and security. While in similar study FRANCIS (2019) revealed that majority of the government employees invest in various investment opportunities and maintain a better saving habit to improve their social and economic status. J & DR. S BHUVANESWARI (2022) concluded that employees are aware of various investments and are satisfied with their investments. Any investor's primary investment goal is to meet future needs and generate regular income. He/she generally prefers to invest in the medium term with quarterly payment options and explored that Investors consider fundamental security as a significant factor affecting investment while liquidity is considered the least factor affecting the investment (Ramaya, 2022). She also explored that most employees get the source of information about investment avenues through friends, families and media and they prefer the banking sector to invest with priority basis. ALPHONSE, (2019) noted that private sector employees are more aware of various investment options such as government bonds and securities, stock markets, mutual funds, gold and real estate. Gold is still preferred to some extent, especially among women. Due to consistent appreciation of the yellow metal (gold) regularly, gold is still an excellent investment option.

RESEARCH GAP

Investing money is one of the major priorities of people today. The change exists in the investment pattern and criteria behind evaluation of different investment avenue periodically. Government as well as private sector employees are getting better salary now-a-days. But their investment decisions being affected by different factors like time constraint, lack of knowledge about different investment avenues, return on investment, tax benefits, future planning for retirement etc. Post-Covid, it was observed that the thinking and behaviour of people changed in terms of saving and investing money for future. People became more flexible to follow the attitude of living in present and taking moderate risk in life. Today there are different options for salaried persons to invest their hard-earned money. Based on the available literature it was found that very few research studies conducted analysing the factors affecting the investment pattern of public sector employees and private sector employees; and comparing their behaviour in post-covid 19 pandemic time. This research gap will be bridged with the present study analysing the factors affecting the investment behaviour of public vs. private sector employees in Gandhinagar and Kalol city of Gujarat after the Covid-19 epidemic.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present study aims to measure a comparative analysis of investment pattern of Public and private sector employees. 160 responses were selected out of 210, as others were not complete and reliable, thus the response rate was 76.19%. The questionnaire included questions about demographic details in part – 1 like City, Gender, Age, Marital status, Occupation, Monthly Income, Education qualification, Number of kids and Average income tax payment and in part-2 included the research variables like Investment intention (5 scale items), Return on investment (4 scale items), Influencers (7 scale items), Perceived Risk (5 scale items), Investment Scheme (4 scale items), Investment pattern (4 scale items) using 5 – point Likert scale. The survey was conducted in Gandhinagar and Kalol regions of Gujarat state. The samples were selected using convenient sampling method. Independent sample - T

test, ANOVA and Spearman's Rank correlation analysis were employed to assess effect of different variables on investment pattern and intention of the respondents. The following are the hypothesis for the study:

H1: There is significant relationship between demographic variables and investment intention (Ha), Return on Investment (Hb), Impact of influencers (Hc), Perceived Risk (Hd), (Investment Scheme (He) and Investment Pattern (Hf).

H2: There is a significant (monotonic) relationship between Investment Intention and Return on Investment

H3: There is a significant (monotonic) relationship between Investment Intention and Influencers.

H4: There is a significant (monotonic) relationship between Investment Intention and Perceived Risk.

H5: There is a significant (monotonic) relationship between Investment Intention and Investment Scheme.

H6: There is a significant (monotonic) relationship between Investment Intention and Investment Pattern.

DATA ANALYSIS

Demographic profile of respondents:

Following table-1 depicts that majority of the respondents are male (74.4%) and married (65.5%). Sample data was conducted from two cities Kalol (60.6%) and Gandhinagar (39.4%) of Gujarat. Age group wise data shows that 20-30 years respondents were 40%, 31-40 years were 33% and 27% were above 40 years of age. 34.4% respondents were not having any kid, while 30% were having single child, 25% respondents having two kids and 10.6% were having 3 kids. The data shows that the majority of the respondents are graduate (43.7%) and Post graduate (46.3%) and 36% respondents were having monthly income 20,001 – 50,000 INR. Public and private sector employees were selected on equal ratio (50-50%) for the comparison of their investment pattern.

Table-1 Demographic profile of respondents

Demographic variable		Frequency	Percentage
City	Kalol	97	60.6
	Gandhinagar	63	39.4
Gender	Male	119	74.4
	Female	41	25.6
Age	20 - 30	66	40
	31 - 40	55	33
	Above 40	44	27
Marital status	Married	105	65.6
	Unmarried	55	34.4
Number of kids below 18 years in family	0	55	34.4
	1	48	30
	2	40	25
	3	17	10.6

Educational Qualification	Under Graduate	11	6.9
	Graduate	70	43.7
	Post graduate	74	46.3
	Others	5	3.1
Occupation	Private Sector Employee	80	50
	Government Employee	80	50
Monthly Income	Less than 20,000	28	17.5
	20,001 - 50,000	58	36
	50,001 - 1,00,000	50	31
	Above 1,00,000	24	15.5
Average Income Tax payment per year	Less than 25,000 INR	75	46.9
	25,001 - 50,000 INR	43	26.9
	50,001 - 75,000 INR	22	13.7
	Above 75,000 INR	20	12.5
Percentage of your income you invest per year	0 - 20%	77	48
	21 - 40%	41	26
	41 - 60%	42	26

Source: Authors' Primary data analysis, 2023

RELIABILITY ANALYSIS

Reliability analysis is used to measure the internal level of consistency of the scale items used in the research study whether they are consistent in nature or not. If consistency found, it means the scale items are highly correlate with each other and the scale is said to be consistent. To measure this consistency, reliability analysis is used through Cronbach's Alpha test (Cronbach, 1951). The following table-2 shows the result of reliability through Cronbach's Alpha values:

Table-2 Reliability analysis

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of items in a scale
Investment Intention	.849	5
Return on Investment	.774	4
Influencer	.881	6
Perceived Risk	.830	5
Investment Scheme	.791	4
Investment Pattern	.873	4

Demographic profile of the respondents affects their investment decision making process the most. They decide for investing their hard-earned money in different schemes for investment after self-study as well as seeking the advice of their peers, friends, relatives or investment advisors. Generally, investment advisor's advice is given more importance by the investors. Their work profile whether public sector or private sector is having significant impact on their choice. The following table shows relationship among different demographic factors of a respondents and selected scale used for the study like investment intension, return on investment, impact of influencers, perceived risk, investment scheme, investment pattern of them through application of t-test (City, Gender, Marital Status, Occupation with other variables) and ANOVA (age, education qualification, monthly income, percentage of the

income used for investment with other variables) and the significant p-values are shown in the table along with the mean value for the respective variables.

The following are the research hypothesis for the present study for applying T-test and ANOVA

H1: There is significant relationship between demographic variables [city (1.1), Gender (1.2), Marital status (1.3), occupation (1.4), Age (1.5), Education Qualification (1.6), Monthly Income (1.7) and percentage of income (1.8)] and investment intention (Ha), Return on Investment (Hb), Impact of influencers (Hc), Perceived Risk (Hd), (Investment Scheme (He) and Investment Pattern (Hf).

H2: There is a significant (monotonic) relationship between Investment Intention and Return on Investment.

H3: There is a significant (monotonic) relationship between Investment Intention and Influencers.

H4: There is a significant (monotonic) relationship between Investment Intention and Perceived Risk.

H5: There is a significant (monotonic) relationship between Investment Intention and Investment Scheme.

H6: There is a significant (monotonic) relationship between Investment Intention and Investment Pattern.

Table-3 P values for T-Test and ANOVA

Demographic Factors		Investment Intension		Return on Investment		Influencers		Perceived Risk		Investment Scheme		Investment Pattern	
		Mean	p-Value	Mean	p-Value	Mean	p-Value	Mean	p-Value	Mean	p-Value	Mean	p-Value
City	Kalol	3.81	0.008	3.73	0.344	3.53	0.231	3.63	0.026	3.77	0.3	3.7	0.3
	Gandhi nagar	3.68		3.63		3.4		3.35		3.65		3.4	
Gender	Male	3.73	0.313	3.68	0.553	3.44	0.218	3.43	0.012	3.7	0.3	3.7	0.3
	Female	3.85		3.76		3.59		3.78		3.8		3.8	

Marital Status	Married	3.84	0.043	3.76	0.121	3.51	0.38	3.72	0.00	3.8	0.036	3.081	0.006
	Unmarried	3.62		3.59		3.41		3.17		3.59		3.52	
Occupation	Private Sector Employee	3.82	0.238	3.76	0.259	3.5	0.635	3.62	0.014	3.78	0.322	3.78	0.388
	Government Employee	3.7		3.64		3.45		3.41		3.68		3.64	
Age	20 - 30	3.7	0.442	3.62	0.43	3.48	0.971	3.29	0.006	3.68	0.771	3.58	0.017
	31 - 40	3.76		3.72		3.48		3.66		3.76		3.78	
	Above 40	3.86		3.8		3.45		3.7		3.75		3.82	
Educational Qualification	Under Graduate	3.64	0.794	3.73	0.393	3.09	0.239	3.27	0.681	3.36	0.124	3.64	0.399
	Graduate	3.77		3.71		3.49		3.57		3.69		3.74	
	Post graduate	3.76		3.65		3.53		3.5		3.8		3.68	
	Others	4		4.2		3.4		3.6		4		3.8	
Monthly Income	Less than 20,000	3.21	0.00	3.07	0.00	3.07	0.003	3	0.00	3.32	0.003	3.01	0.00
	20,001 - 50,000	3.95		3.93		3.62		3.5		3.83		3.78	
	50,001 - 1,00,000	3.84		3.78		3.54		3.76		3.8		3.86	

	Above 1,00,000	3.79		3.71		3.46		3.67		3.79		3.92
Percentage of your income you invest per year	0 - 20%	3.81	0.671	3.77	0.349	3.48	0.845	3.42	0.271	3.69	0.747	3.657
	21 - 40%	3.76		3.71		3.51		3.61		3.78	0.737	3.68
	41 - 60%	3.69		3.57		3.43		3.62		3.74	0.736	3.67

The result of independent sample T-test in the above table, the researchers can conclude the following information,

1. City is having significant relationship with investment intention ($p=0.008$) and perceived risk ($p=0.026$). So, respondents from Kalol and Gandhinagar, people from Kalol invest for improving their standard of living and to manage the future uncertainty (mean=3.81) and consider the importance of risk factors while investing in mutual fund (mean=3.63) compared to respondents from Gandhinagar (mean=3.68 and mean=3.35 respectively for investment intention and perceived risk).
2. Gender is having significant relationship with perceived risk ($p=0.012$) and compared to male (mean=3.43), females (mean=3.78) give more importance to invest in the mutual fund avenue as they want to avoid risk.
3. Marital status is having significant relationship with investment intention ($p=0.043$), perceived risk ($p=0.00$), Investment Scheme ($p=0.036$) and Investment Pattern ($p=0.046$) and for all these factors married investors having strong investment intention to invest in attractive investment scheme with improved investment pattern where less risk is associated.
4. A significant relationship found for occupation and perceived risk ($p=0.014$). While comparing public and private sector employees, private sector employees take more risk in terms of investment (mean=3.62) compared to public sector employees (mean=3.41)

The result of ANOVA in the above table, the conclusion can be drawn below:

1. Age is having significant impact on investment pattern ($p=0.017$). Among the respondents, above 40 years age people take moderate risk, considering relevant factors for investment and invest only in the safe schemes for long term return with mean value of 3.82, followed by the age group of 31-40 years respondents (mean=3.78) and 21-30 years aged respondents (mean=3.58).
2. Monthly income is having significant relationship with all the study variables viz. investment intension ($p=0.00$), return on investment ($p=0.00$), investment influencers ($p=0.003$), perceived risk ($p=0.00$), investment scheme ($p=0.00$) and investment pattern of respondents ($p=0.00$).

3. For the variables, Education and percentage of income for investment in mutual fund does not have any significant relationship with investment intension, return on investment, perceived risk, investment scheme, investment pattern of respondents.

Thus, here H1.1a, H1.1d, H1.2d, H1.3a, H1.3d, H1.3f, H1.4d, H1.5f, H1.7a, H1.7b, H1.7c, H1.7d, H1.7e, and H1.7f are accepted as per the above p values in the table-3.

Spearman's rho Analysis

Spearman correlation (Spearman's rho) is a measure used to study the correlation or strength and direction between two variables selected for the study. Here this is an appropriate test to be used to study the monotonic relationship between investment intention and other variables (Return on Investment, Perceived Risk, Impact of influencers, Investment Scheme and Investment Pattern) as the data we are having is an ordinal data.

H2: There is a significant (monotonic) relationship between Investment Intention and Return on Investment

H3: There is a significant (monotonic) relationship between Investment Intention and Influencers.

H4: There is a significant (monotonic) relationship between Investment Intention and Perceived Risk.

H5: There is a significant (monotonic) relationship between Investment Intention and Investment Scheme.

H6: There is a significant (monotonic) relationship between Investment Intention and Investment Pattern.

In the following table-4 Spearman's rho is applied to analysis the monotonic relationship among different variables and the value is mentioned in it:

Table-4 Spearman's Rho values

Correlation Coefficient		
Spearman's Rho	Investment Intention (Correlation-Value)	N
Return on Investment	.816 ^{**}	160
Influencers	.663 ^{**}	160
Perceived Risk	.447 ^{**}	160
Investment Scheme	.512 ^{**}	160
Investment Pattern	.592 ^{**}	160

In Spearman's correlation analysis, the value of correlation coefficient ranges from +1 to -1. +1 means perfect positive (Strong positive) correlation exists between the two variables while -1 means perfect negative (Strong negative) correlation exists between the two variables. The meaning of 0 value of Spearman's rho means that there is no relationship between the two variables at the study. The value greater than 0 and nearer to +1 shows strong positive correlation while value greater than 0 but nearer to 0 only shows weaker positive correlation as well as values less than 0 but nearer to 0 shows weaker negative correlation while value less than 0 and nearer to -1 means there exists strong negative correlation between the variables at study.

The detailed information about different values shown in the following table-5.

Table-5 Spearman’s Rho- Correlations

Spearman’s Rho - Correlations							
		Investment Intention	Return on Investment	Influencers	Perceived Risk	Investment Scheme	Investment Pattern
Investment Intension	Correlation Coefficient	1	.816**	.663**	.447**	.512**	.592**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.000	<.000	<.000	<.000	<.000
	N	160	160	160	160	160	160
Return on Investment	Correlation Coefficient	.816**	1.000	.500**	.355**	.456**	.505**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	.	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	160	160	160	160	160	160
Influencers	Correlation Coefficient	.663**	.500**	1.000	.215**	.404**	.332**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	.	.006	<.001	<.001
	N	160	160	160	160	160	160
Perceived Risk	Correlation Coefficient	.447**	.355**	.215**	1.000	.261**	.278**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	.006	.	<.001	<.001
	N	160	160	160	160	160	160
Investment Scheme	Correlation Coefficient	.512**	.456**	.404**	.261**	1.000	.327**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	.	<.001
	N	160	160	160	160	160	160
Investment Pattern	Correlation Coefficient	.592**	.505**	.332**	.278**	.327**	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	.
	N	160	160	160	160	160	160

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The above data leads to the conclusion that there exists a monotonic relationship between Investment Intention and Return on Investment (H2) it means these two variables are having $r(158) = 0.816$, $p < 0.000$ [r (df)=r value, p= p value] stronger positive correlation nearer to perfect correlation i.e. H2 is accepted. For H3 with $r(158) = .663$, $p < 0.000$ Investment Intention and impact of influencer are having strong positive correlation it means both the variables increase simultaneously and vice versa, Hence H3 is accepted. In case of H4, $r(158) = .447$, $p < 0.000$ Investment Intention and Perceived Risk are moderately positively correlated with the acceptance of H4. Hypothesis H5 is accepted measuring correlation between Investment Intention and Investment Scheme with $r(158) = .512$, $p < 0.000$ strong

positive correlation and H6 is also accepted regarding measuring correlation between Investment intention and Investment Pattern with $r(158) = .592$, $p < 0.000$ with strong positive correlation.

CONCLUSION

When investors lack the suggestions of advisors and having limited knowledge in share market investment option, limited amount to invest, they generally prefer the mutual fund as an investment avenue. The present study investigated about investment pattern of such investors from two different cities of Gujarat state and concluded that the investors from Kalol city invest with the investment motives like improving their standard of living, to cope up with the future uncertainty including medical and natural calamities. Female investors chooses the mutual fund as an investment option to manage risk level to moderate. Married people also avoid taking more risk in other investment avenues. The main focus of this study was to compare public and private sector employees' investment behaviour and the result found that private sector employees are taking more risks as they are habituated to take risk due to their segment of work while public sector employees take moderate risk in terms of investments. This is because public sector employees having stable regular income being offered and different retirement plans like pension which provide them guaranteed return and they are having less or almost no control over this investment so they are found conservative in nature in the matter of other investment options to be selected while in case of private sector employees, their income depends on their potential every time and their retirement income totally depends on their contribution in various investment plans where they contribute major portion of their salary to reap the benefits in future. Thus, they have more control behind their investment avenue selection.

RECOMMENDATION

The present study focused on the current earnings and the choice of investment and pattern of investment and compared public and private sector employees' behaviour in this regard. Still there exist scope for further inclusion of the study of retirement savings plans and investment allocation like the percentage of income they would like to save for future, what type of return they want, which investment option they want to choose, and comparison for the level of financial literacy of the employees from both the sectors. Such study can be repeated in the other part of the state or country which may lead to different results.

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